

Quality in Diamond Open Access Publishing: guidelines, policies and templates

Iryna Kuchma & Milica Ševkušić
EIFL

Reviewed by Aleš Pogačnik
Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts
Ljubljana, Slovenia

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1. Introduction

Diamond Open Access (OA)¹ journals are often managed by small teams with limited resources, making it difficult to keep pace with evolving policy developments, best practices and technical requirements. Support and guidance are needed to help these journals adopt current best practices.

The guidelines and policy and document templates in this document are designed to help Diamond OA journals establish themselves as trustworthy sources of knowledge by providing practical tools to enhance quality and align with best practices in OA publishing. These non-exhaustive materials build upon established frameworks, including the [DOAJ's Basic Criteria](#), the [Best Practices Checklist for Diamond OA Publishers](#), and the [Diamond Open Access Standard \(DOAS\)](#) developed by the [Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models To Advance Scholarly Communication \(DIAMAS\)](#) project, taking into account the specific challenges faced by Diamond OA journals in Africa and aiming to provide practical, adaptable solutions.

The document includes:

- Essential elements of Diamond OA journals
- [Journal Policies Template](#), as well as [Author Statement](#), [Conflict of Interest](#) and [Licence Agreement](#) templates
- Technical guidelines: [elements to include in article landing pages](#) and the [full-text](#) of the article, [displaying licensing information](#), depositing metadata, general advice regarding [journal websites](#) and [accessibility](#).

This document does not provide detailed instructions on the structure or content of Author Guidelines, as these vary widely across disciplines. Instead, journals are advised to draw on reporting standards, citation guidelines, and discipline-specific best practices when developing their own guidelines.

2. Essential elements of Diamond OA journals

[DOAJ's Basic Criteria](#) and [Diamond Open Access Standard \(DOAS\)](#) were used as a starting point in defining these baseline requirements.

1. The journal has an ISSN (print and/or eISSN), which is clearly displayed on the journal website and can be checked in the [ISSN registry](#).

¹In this publishing model, often referred to as Diamond Open Access publishing, no fees are charged to authors to publish and readers to read.

2. The journal has a regular schedule of publication, either issue by issue or via continuous publication.
3. All information provided on the journal website is up-to-date.
4. The journal does not charge fees to authors for publishing or to readers for reading and articles are made immediately available online upon publication.
5. The information that authors do not pay Article Processing Charges (APCs) or any other charges are clearly stated on the journal website (preferably in journal policies and author guidelines).
6. The journal has its own dedicated URL and a homepage that is accessible from any location.
7. The information about the mission (i.e. in a journal mission statement), aims and scope, as well as the languages in which manuscripts can be submitted is displayed on the journal website.
8. The journal publishes scholarly content and contains original research articles and the criteria for acceptance of manuscripts are defined and publicly available on the journal website.
9. The journal has an editorial board (with editorial board members from more than one institution) and may also have other editorial bodies. The composition of the editorial bodies is publicly displayed (i.e. with the editorial team names, functions and roles; affiliations) on the journal's website, as well as on any platforms hosting the journal's content.
10. Manuscripts submitted to the journal have passed peer review by at least two peer reviewers before they were published. The information about the peer review process is publicly displayed on the journal website.
11. Clear and detailed author guidelines are publicly available on the journal website. They include at least:
 - An explanation of the types of manuscripts that a journal will consider.
 - A detailed style guide (that includes referencing style).
 - A description of how to submit an article.

3. Journal policies template and supporting documents

Journal policies help authors understand what is expected of them and how their work will be handled, from submission to publication. For readers, clear policies build trust by showing that the journal follows fair and consistent practices. They also make it easier for indexing services and research assessment bodies to see that the journal meets recognized standards.

EIFL has developed a journal policies template as a structured framework that Diamond OA journals can easily adapt to their needs. It covers the key policies on journal scope, ownership, open access, indexing, and archiving. It defines editorial responsibilities, peer review processes, ethical standards, and provides guidelines for authorship, checking and dealing

with plagiarism, and conflict of interest. It also includes policies on using generative AI (artificial intelligence) tools, research transparency (data, code, and protocol sharing), complaints, misconduct investigations, retractions and post-publication discussions. Copyright, licensing, self-archiving, and metadata policies are also addressed.

By using this policies template and aligning practices with it, journals can ensure compliance with best practices in scholarly publishing.

Policies should be displayed on the journal website. If a journal is hosted on a platform hosting multiple journals, the platform should allow for displaying journal policies on dedicated pages (rather than as attachments).

The following documents can be found in the annexes:

- [Journal policies template](#)
- [Supporting documents templates](#)

4. What to display on article landing pages

(Note: Bold typeface indicates mandatory elements.)

1. Article title

2. Full names of authors

3. ORCID (Open Researchers and Contributor ID - personal persistent identifier). See: [ORCID iD display guidelines](#).

4. Institutional affiliations of authors

Institutional affiliations should contain the full name and address of the institution, e.g. University, Faculty/Institute, City, Country.

5. ROR ID (Institutional persistent identifier)

See: [Logos and display guidelines](#).

6. Journal title, volume, issue, publication year, and article number (or pagination)

The journal title should be the same as registered in the [ISSN International Registry](#). Don't use any unofficial translated or abbreviated forms.

7. Article type (e.g. research article, review, short communication, etc.)

8. A persistent identifier for the article: DOI (Digital Object Identifier) or ARK (Archival Resource Key), Handle or URN

DOI (and other PIDs) should always be displayed as a full URL link. See: [Display guidelines - Crossref](#).

9. Abstract

A brief summary of an article that helps readers quickly understand its purpose and significance, highlighting the research questions, methods, key findings, and main conclusions. It should be between 150–250 words; for non-English articles, often also in English (with translated title and keywords).

10. Keywords

Specific terms or phrases that capture the main topics of the study. It is a good idea to enrich author-provided keywords with terms from relevant controlled vocabularies.

11. Supporting information

Provide links to related research outputs (e.g. preprints, and registered studies, etc.). Use persistent identifiers to establish links with the related content.

12. Data availability statement

It should provide the details of the data availability, including the DOI linking to it. If the data is restricted in any way and/or is not being made available within the journal publication, a statement from the author should be provided to explain why. See Annex 1: [Journal policies template](#).

13. Author contributions

Contributions include not only writing but also the activities related to the conceptualisation and execution of the research, collection and production of the research data/materials, analysis and interpretation. Use the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) to describe the key types of contributions made to the article. How to implement: [How to implement CRediT](#).

14. Conflict of interest statement. See Annex 2: [Supporting documents](#).

15. Funding information

This section typically includes details about grants, sponsorships, institutional support, or other financial resources that contributed to the study. It often specifies the funding organisations or agencies, grant numbers, and any relevant funding acknowledgements. Use ROR IDs of institutions and funding organizations. See: [Logos and display guidelines](#).

16. References

Use standardised citation styles (e.g., APA, MLA, Chicago) to ensure consistency and facilitate accurate identification of sources. When deciding which citation style to use in your journal(s), you should give preference to those that include DOI or URL in reference list entries (e.g. APA, Chicago). Always display DOIs and URLs as links.

17. Copyright information

Specify who has the legal rights to the article. Diamond OA journals should allow authors to retain copyright.

18. Licence information

See below: [Displaying Creative Commons licences](#).

19. Publisher's name

Display the publisher's name prominently on the journal website. Use the official name, as registered in the [ISSN International Registry](#).

20. ISSN and eISSN

ISSN (International Standard Serial Number) and eISSN (electronic ISSN) are unique identifiers assigned to print and electronic versions of a serial publication, respectively. Display these numbers prominently on a journal website to make it easy for users to locate and verify this information. See: [What is an ISSN? | ISSN](#).

21. Link(s) to access the full text

5. Recommendations for publishing the full text of journal articles

5.1. What to include in the full text

Publishers are sometimes unsure about what information should be included in the full text of published articles. In many cases, the layout and structure of full-text documents still follow a design logic inherited from print publishing. As a result, key metadata elements, such as persistent identifiers, are often missing from the full text or are included without being rendered as interactive links. Similarly, elements like the ISSN may be omitted under the assumption that they are available elsewhere on the journal website.

Publishers should be aware that most users now access full-text documents directly through search engines, bypassing article landing pages. Due to this, it is essential to include all relevant metadata within the full-text file itself to ensure the article is properly identified, cited, and linked within scholarly infrastructure.

The following list outlines the key information that should be embedded in the full-text document. Bold typeface indicates mandatory elements.

1. Journal title

It should be the same as registered in the [ISSN International Registry](#). Don't use any unofficial translated or abbreviated forms.

2. Online and/or Print ISSN. Include both, if available. See: [What is an ISSN? | ISSN](#).

3. Journal volume, issue (if available), article number (or pages).

4. Persistent identifier for the article: DOI (Digital Object Identifier) or ARK (Archival Resource Key), Handle or URN. DOI (and other PIDs) should always be displayed as a full URL link. See: [Display guidelines - Crossref](#).

5. Article type (e.g. research article, case study, review, short communication, etc.).

6. Article title

7. Full names of authors

8. ORCID (Open Researchers and Contributor ID - personal persistent identifier). Display it as a full URL link. If there is no space in the usual author information block, provide a list of authors along with relevant identifiers in a footnote or on the final page. See: [ORCID iD display guidelines](#).

9. Institutional affiliations of authors

Institutional affiliations should contain the full name and address of the institution, e.g. University, Faculty/Institute, City, Country.

10. ROR ID (Institutional persistent identifier)

Display it as a full link. If there is no space in the usual author information block, provide a list of authors along with relevant identifiers in a footnote or on the final page. See: [Logos and display guidelines](#).

11. Abstract

A brief summary of an article that helps readers quickly understand its purpose and significance, highlighting the research questions, methods, key findings, and main conclusions. It should be between 150 - 250 words.

12. Keywords

Specific terms or phrases that capture the main topics of the study. It is a good idea to enrich author-provided keywords with terms from relevant controlled vocabularies.

13. The text of the article

14. Supporting information

Provide links to related research outputs (e.g. research data deposited in repositories, preprints, and registered studies, etc.). Use persistent identifiers to establish links with the related content.

15. Data availability statement providing the details of the data availability, including the DOI linking to it. If the data is restricted in any way and/or is not being made available within the journal publication, a statement from the author should be provided to explain why. See Annex 1: [Journal policies template](#).

16. Author contributions

Contributions include not only writing but also the activities related to the conceptualisation and execution of the research, collection and production of the research data/materials, analysis and interpretation. Use the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) to describe the key types of contributions made to the article. How to implement: [How to implement CRediT](#).

17. Conflict of interest statement. See Annex 1: [Journal policies template](#).

18. Funding information

This section typically includes details about grants, sponsorships, institutional support, or other financial resources that contributed to the study. It often specifies the funding organisations or agencies, grant numbers, and any relevant funding acknowledgements. Use ROR IDs of institutions and funding organizations. See: [Logos and display guidelines](#).

19. References

Use standardised citation styles (e.g., APA, MLA, Chicago) to ensure consistency and facilitate accurate identification of sources. When deciding which citation style to use in your journal(s), you should give preference to those that include DOI or URL in reference list entries (e.g. APA, Chicago). Always display DOIs and URLs as links.

20. Copyright information

Specify who has the legal rights to the article. Diamond OA journals should allow authors to retain copyright.

21. Licence information

See below: [Displaying Creative Commons licences](#).

22. Publisher's name

Display the publisher's name prominently. Use the official name, as registered in the [ISSN International Registry](#).

5.2. Full text in multiple formats

Providing journal articles in multiple formats (PDF, HTML, EPUB, XML, and plain text) improves accessibility, discoverability, and preservation. Using XML-first workflows, where content is initially created or converted (e.g. from DOCX) into XML format and then (automatically) transformed into multiple output formats (e.g., PDF, HTML, EPUB), is recommended as this ensures consistent metadata embedding.²

However, providing journal articles in multiple formats requires technical and financial resources, e.g investing in conversion tools and staff operating format conversion workflows. If resources are limited, journals can prioritize commonly used formats (e.g., PDF and HTML) and plan for a gradual expansion of format options through collaboration and partnerships with universities, libraries, or open-access initiatives.

General recommendations

- Use open-source, Unicode-supporting fonts. See: [Open-Source Unicode Typefaces](#) (Wikipedia).
- Avoid multi-column layout, as this can make it difficult for accessibility assistants and indexing services to process the text.
- Do not use outdated file formats (e.g. DOC, RTF, WPD, etc.).

JATS XML

- Embed detailed metadata, including [CRedit](#) information, copyright and licence information, and conflict of interest statements in the full text. Learn more: See: [JATS4R](#)

PDF

- Ensure that the PDF version is PDF/A compliant. In most typesetting tools it is possible to generate PDF/A files.
- Do not restrict access to the full text (e.g. by preventing text copying or converting text in PDFs to outlines).
- If PDFs include abstracts in another language, make sure that the key metadata (Title, author affiliations, abstract, keywords) are provided in that language.

6. Displaying Creative Commons licences

Properly displaying Creative Commons (CC) licences remains a challenge for many journals. Frequent issues include not displaying a licence at all, mismatching the licence name and the licence logo, linking to the wrong licence, or presenting inconsistent information across

² Resources: [Journal Publishing Tag Library NISO JATS Version 1.4 \(ANSI/NISO Z39.96-2024\)](#)

different parts of the journal website (e.g. declaring one licence in the journal policies and another in full-text articles).

This section provides guidance on where Creative Commons licences should be displayed and how to display them correctly.

General considerations

- Use Creative Commons licences (please note that version 4.0 is the latest international recommended version). Avoid custom non-standardized licence statements, as they can't be displayed in a machine-readable way.
- Always link the licence name to the licence website.
- Use the latest version of the licence.
- Make sure that licence information is consistent across the publishing platform (in journal policies, footer, landing pages, full text).

Journal policies

- Licensing policy is usually addressed together with the copyright policy:
“Authors retain copyright of the published papers and grant to the publisher the non-exclusive right to publish the article, to be cited as its original publisher in case of reuse, and to distribute it in all forms and media. Articles will be distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](#) licence.” See Annex 1: [Journal policies template](#)
- In the journal policy, link the licence name to the licence web page:
“Articles will be distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](#) licence.”

Article landing pages

- Licence logo.
- Licence name (link it to the licence website).
- A short description of licence terms.
- The licence information is usually accompanied with copyright information.

Example

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Authors retain copyright of the published papers and grant to the publisher the right to publish the article, to be cited as its original publisher in case of reuse, and to distribute it in all forms and media. Articles will be distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](#).

Note: It is also acceptable to display licensing information in the website footer. In this case, indicate that the licence displayed applies to the entire website content unless otherwise indicated: “Unless otherwise indicated, the content of this website is published under license: [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#).”

Full-text article

- Licence logo.
- Licence name (link it to the licence website).
- A short description of licence terms (optional).
- The licence information is usually accompanied with copyright information.

Example

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Authors retain copyright of the published papers and grant to the publisher the right to publish the article, to be cited as its original publisher in case of reuse, and to distribute it in all forms and media. Articles will be distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution International License](#) (CC BY 4.0).

There is no fixed place for this information. It can be placed either on the first or on the last page of the full-text article.

Machine-readable metadata

- Submit licensing information when registering DOIs (or other PIDs). Learn more: [License information - Crossref](#).
- Include licensing information in HTML meta tags. This is easy in platforms such as OJS or Janeway.
- Expose licensing information via OAI-PMH.

7. Depositing metadata with PID registration agencies

- Deposit rich metadata about publications, including bibliographic references and abstracts, when registering persistent identifiers for articles in line with the recommendations of the [Initiative for Open Citations \(I4OC\)](#) and [Initiative for Open Abstracts \(I4OA\)](#).
- Include PIDs for authors, organisations and related research outputs (e.g. research data).
- Include metadata in multiple languages, if available.
- Include access level and licensing information.

Release the metadata into the public domain using the CC0 licence, e.g. by including the following statement in the journal policies: “The journal metadata are freely accessible to all, and freely reusable by all, under the terms of the Creative Commons [Universal \(CC0 1.0\)](#)”

[Public Domain Dedication licence](#).” See Annex 1: [Journal policies template](#).

8. Journal website

If possible, use free and open source software (FOSS) platforms that support the entire publishing workflow, from manuscript submission and peer review to content display (e.g. [Open Journal Systems](#), [Janeway](#), [Kotahi](#)). These platforms also enable metadata display in line with widely adopted metadata schemas (e.g. [Dublin Core](#), [DataCite](#), [Crossref](#), [JATS XML](#), etc.) and support metadata exchange through standard protocols such as ([Open Access Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting – OAI-PMH](#), [REST API](#), HTTPS, etc.). All these features are more difficult and costly to ensure in custom-made platforms based on generic software solutions that are not specifically adjusted to software management.

Popular FOSS solutions (e.g. [Open Journal Systems](#), [Janeway](#), [Kotahi](#)) come with a set of inbuilt interface themes ensuring responsive design and a clear menu structure. Use default themes (normally, you can customize colors and fonts by editing a stylesheet) for the journal website to ensure easier maintenance and compatibility with future upgrades. Be cautious when using non-default themes, as they may not always be available in future software updates. Make sure that software is regularly updated and that back-up procedures are in place.

Managing a publishing platform based on free and open-source software (FOSS) can be challenging, especially when dedicated IT support or reliable server infrastructure is not readily available. For this reason, it is advisable to use established continental, national or institutional publishing platforms based on FOSS solutions, if such platforms are available. These shared infrastructures can provide the necessary technical support, maintenance, and sustainability that individual journals may not be able to ensure on their own.

8.1. Website accessibility for people with visual impairment

Making journal websites more accessible to blind and visually impaired people is important. However, many Diamond OA journals have limited budgets to cover the costs of making websites accessible, and journal technical staff may lack the technical skills needed to set up and maintain assistive technologies. It is recommended that journals develop a strategy and plan for accessibility. If alternatives are unaffordable, start with cost-free improvements. The following recommendations offer practical ways to improve accessibility, even with limited resources:

- Use clear and simple menu labels.
- Provide the full text in HTML (which works well on mobile devices) and machine-readable formats like EPUB or XML (which are suitable for users with screen readers).
- Make colors accessible for people with color vision impairment. Avoid using color alone to convey meaning, ensure good contrast (e.g. black text on a white background), and use patterns or labels when necessary.

- Avoid small and thin fonts, and make sure the text doesn't blend into the background.
- Allow users to adjust the font size.
- Add descriptions for images. If you include charts, figures, or images, add a short text description (ALT text) for people using screen readers.
- Help screen readers understand your site by using headings – H1, H2, H3.
- If users need to fill out forms (e.g. for submissions), label fields clearly and explain errors in plain language. Avoid CAPTCHA tests that require clicking images as some users can't complete them.
- If your site has content in multiple languages, make it easy to switch between them.

Many tools that can help you improve accessibility for blind or otherwise visually impaired people are available, but few are free. One free and easy to implement tool is [Sienna Accessibility Widget](#), which helps adjust text display (font size, line height, dyslexia font, contrast and saturation adjustments, etc.).

You can use free tools like [WAVE Web Accessibility Evaluation Tools](#) to check if your website has issues that may present obstacles for people with visual impairment. Also, ask people with visual impairment to test the site and give feedback.

However, authoring tools are a major problem: it is usually difficult or impossible to create accessible tables and forms using office tools. Watch this webinar to learn more about available tools and strategies: [OpenAIRE coffee break on e-accessibility](#).

Resources

[DOAJ's Basic criteria – updated and rewritten in plain English](#)

[Best Practices checklist for Diamond OA publishers - DIAMAS](#)

Consortium of the DIAMAS project. (2024). The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13820036>

[Better Practices in Journal Metadata](#)

[JATS4R](#)

[Toolsuite Articles | CAP portal](#)

[Guidelines | CAP portal](#)

Bowker, L., Pölonen, J., Laakso, M., & Redhead, C. (2024). Deliverable D4.6 – Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) in scholarly communication - working with communities to develop resources for multilingualism, gender equity and accessible and inclusive websites (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13786107>

Annex 1: Journal policies template

This is a generic policies template for Diamond OA journals. It can easily be adjusted to include discipline-specific considerations. The policies template is aligned with the Diamond Open Access Standard developed by the DIAMAS project and it can help journals meet policy-related requirements for acceptance in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).

Edit the red text or remove it if it's not relevant for your journal. The blue text contains instructions and should be removed when you finish drafting your policies.

General information

The journal *Journal's title* is dedicated to [define aims and scope].

You may also provide a short history of the journal, the previous title (if applicable, etc.)

The journal is owned and published by _____.³

The journal is financially supported by _____.⁴

The journal *Journal's title* publishes original papers that have not been published previously. (Define article types: scientific articles, reviews, communications, letters, conference papers, etc.).

Journal's title is an open access journal that doesn't charge any fees either to readers to read, nor to authors to publish.

Contributions to the journal shall be submitted in language(s), with summaries in language(s). The journal is open to all researchers globally, regardless of gender, career stage or ethnic and religious affiliation.

The Journal is issued _____ times a year.⁵

The journal is indexed in _____.

Digital copies of the journal are archived in the⁶

³Adjust the statement if the owner and publisher are different entities. If the journal is co-published by multiple entities, mention all of them. Please note that service providers providing online publishing platforms or technical support are usually not publishers. The publisher name declared on the journal website must be the same as that declared in the record on the [ISSN Portal](#). If the information on the ISSN Portal is not up-to-date, contact your National ISSN Centre (if there is one in your country) or the [International ISSN Centre](#) to update the information.

⁴List all entities, programmes and/or projects providing financial support to the journal. Acknowledge in-kind support provided by academic institutions and other entities (e.g. hosting, paid staff assigned to support publishing, etc.), as well as any voluntary contributions.

⁵Continuous publication, where articles are published as soon as they are accepted rather than waiting for a complete issue to be compiled. In this model, articles are usually grouped into volumes or thematic collections.

⁶E.g. LOCKSS, CLOCKSS, Portico.

Editorial policies

Editorial responsibilities

The editorial bodies include: _____

Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor is appointed by _____⁷

Editorial operations related to content and peer review are independent and free from the influence of the entities that support the journal.

The **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board** is responsible for deciding which articles submitted to *Journal's title* will be published. The **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board** is guided by the Editorial Policy and constrained by legal requirements in force regarding libel, copyright infringement and plagiarism.

The **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board** reserves the right to decide not to publish submitted manuscripts in case it is found that they do not meet relevant standards concerning the content and formal aspects. The Editorial Staff will inform the authors whether the manuscript is accepted for publication within _____ from the date of the manuscript submission.

Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board must hold no conflict of interest with regard to the articles they consider for publication. If an Editor feels that there is likely to be a perception of a conflict of interest in relation to their handling of a submission, the selection of reviewers and all decisions on the manuscript shall be made by the _____.⁸

Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board shall evaluate manuscripts for their scientific content free from any racial, gender, sexual, religious, ethnic, or political bias.

The Editor and the Editorial Staff must not use unpublished materials disclosed in submitted manuscripts without the express written consent of the authors. The information and ideas presented in submitted manuscripts shall be kept confidential and must not be used for personal gain.

Variant 1 (in case of single-blind peer review) Editors and the Editorial Staff shall take all reasonable measures to ensure that the reviewers remain anonymous to the authors before, during and after the evaluation process.

⁷List all relevant editorial functions and bodies and describe briefly their roles and procedures to select members of editorial bodies, including the mandate length, regular renewal process, and dissolution of the editorial board.

⁸If the decision whether to accept the manuscript or not is made by the Editorial Board: In case one or more members of the Editorial Staff hold a conflict of interest regarding a submitted manuscript, these members of the Editorial Staff shall withdraw from the selection of reviewers and all decisions related to the manuscript.

Variant 2 (in case of double-blind peer review) Editors and the Editorial Staff shall take all reasonable measures to ensure that the reviewers remain anonymous to the authors before, during and after the evaluation process and the authors remain anonymous to reviewers until the end of the review procedure.

Variant 3 (in case of open peer review) Describe.⁹

Authors' responsibilities

Authors warrant that their manuscript is their original work, that it has not been published before and is not under consideration for publication elsewhere. Parallel submission of the same manuscript to another journal constitutes misconduct and eliminates the manuscript from consideration by **Journal's title**. Please note that posting of preprints on preprint servers or repositories is not considered prior publication.¹⁰ Authors should disclose details of preprint posting upon submission of the manuscript. This must include a link to the location of the preprint. Should the submission be published, the authors are expected to update the information associated with the preprint version on the preprint server/repository to show that a final version has been published in the journal, including the DOI linking directly to the publication.

If a manuscript has previously been submitted elsewhere, authors should provide information about the previous reviewing process and its outcome. This provides an opportunity for authors to detail how subsequent revisions have taken into account previous reviews, and why certain reviewer comments were not taken into account. Information about the author's previous reviewing experience is to the author's advantage: it often helps the editors select more appropriate reviewers.

In case a submitted manuscript is a result of a research project, or its previous version has been presented at a conference in the form of an oral presentation (under the same or similar title), detailed information about the project, the conference, etc. shall be provided **in a footnote / Acknowledgements**.

It is the responsibility of each author to ensure that manuscripts submitted to **Journal's title** are written with ethical standards in mind. **(If necessary, cite the relevant codes of conduct.)**¹¹

⁹For various definitions and models of open peer review, see: Ross-Hellauer, Tony. 2017. 'What Is Open Peer Review? A Systematic Review'. *F1000Research* 6: 588. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11369.2>.

¹⁰In case preprints are allowed, double-blind review is not an option for your journal because it is impossible to ensure the anonymity of authors.

¹¹Depending on the area of science covered by the journal, relevant ethical guidelines may be specified (e.g. research involving human subjects or experimental animals, privacy issues).

Authors affirm that the manuscript contains no unfounded or unlawful statements and does not violate the rights of third parties. The Publisher will not be held legally responsible should there be any claims for compensation.

Reporting standards

Journal's title is committed to serving the research community by ensuring that all articles include enough information to allow others to reproduce the work. A submitted manuscript should contain sufficient detail and references to permit reviewers and, subsequently, readers to verify the claims presented in it - e.g. provide complete details of the methods used, including time frames, etc. Authors are required to review the standards available for many research applications, as for example from [Equator Network for health sciences](#), and use those that are relevant for the reported research applications. The deliberate presentation of false claims is a violation of ethical standards.¹²

Authors are exclusively responsible for the contents of their submissions and must make sure that they have permission from all involved parties to make the content public.¹³ Authors are also exclusively responsible for the contents of their data/supplementary files. Authors affirm that data protection regulations, ethical standards, third party copyright and other rights have been respected in the process of collecting, processing and sharing data.

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Inclusive language

The journal **Journal title** promotes accessible, and inclusive language to ensure that scientific research is widely understood and respectful of all individuals. To promote accessibility, authors should:

- Use clear, simple language that is understandable across disciplines and for non-native speakers (for example non-native English speakers);
- Avoid overly technical or unnecessary terminology, unnecessary complexity, long sentences, repetition, uncommon acronyms and abbreviations, stereotypes, idiomatic speech, slang, and cultural assumptions;
- Explain technical terms when needed;
- Respect diversity and avoid implying superiority of any group based on gender, race, ethnicity, nationality, disability, health status, age, or socio-economic background.
- Use inclusive and appropriate language in relation to race and ethnicity and provide

¹²[If the journal publishes technical papers or book reviews](#): Book reviews and technical papers should be accurate and they should present an objective perspective.

¹³[Authors may be required to provide the proof that they have obtained such permission.](#)

¹⁴[Authors may be required to include evidence that such permission has been granted when submitting their manuscripts.](#)

participants with a comprehensive range of categories and subcategories to choose from when collecting self-reported racial or ethnic identity data, as well as the option to select multiple, not mutually exclusive categories;

- Be cautious in generalizing findings from studies to groups simply on the basis of a shared identity category and provide the rationale behind any racial or ethnic groupings used in the Methods section;
- Where it is necessary to make reference to the indigenous identity of a person or group, use the terms preferred by the person or group. If in doubt, ask the person or group;
- Make a distinction between biological sex and socially constructed gender. Use self-identified pronouns and gender-neutral terms (e.g., "chairperson" instead of "chairman");
- Use "impairment" for medical conditions and "disability" for societal barriers. Avoid discriminatory language and offensive terms (derogatory labelling, depersonalising, stereotyping and emphasising the disability) in relation to the portrayal of people with disabilities (e.g. use 'a person diagnosed with cancer' rather than 'a cancer victim')

Consult also additional resources from C4DISC (Coalition for Diversity and Inclusion in Scholarly Communications): <https://c4disc.org/toolkits-for-equity/>

Authorship

Authors must make sure that only contributors who have significantly contributed to the submission are listed as authors and, conversely, that all contributors who have significantly contributed to the submission are listed as authors. If persons other than authors were involved in important aspects of the research project and the preparation of the manuscript, their contribution should be acknowledged in a footnote or the Acknowledgements section.

As a guide, authors should refer to the criteria for authorship that have been developed by the [International Committee of Medical Journal Editors \(ICMJE\)](#). In order to be named on the author list one must have:

- made substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work; AND
- contributed to the drafting the work, or revising it critically for important intellectual content; AND
- provided final approval of the version to be published; AND
- agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved; AND
- agreed to be named on the author list, and approved of the full author list.

Each author's contribution must be detailed using the [CRediT taxonomy](#).¹⁵

¹⁵In some submission systems this is done by selecting CRediT roles in the article submission form. If this is not supported in your submission system, require authors to include a contribution statement in the manuscript. Example: **Author 1:** review and editing (equal). **Author 2:** Conceptualization (lead); writing – original draft (lead); formal analysis (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). **Author 3:**

The addition or removal of authors during the editorial process will only be permitted only if a justifiable explanation is provided to the editorial team and publisher. Attempts to introduce 'ghost', 'gift' or 'honorary' authorship will be treated as cases of misconduct.

Acknowledgment of sources

Authors are required to properly cite sources that have significantly influenced their research and their manuscript. Information received in a private conversation or correspondence with third parties, in reviewing project applications, manuscripts and similar materials, must not be used without the express written consent of the information source.

When citing or making claims based on data, authors should provide the reference to data in the same way as they cite publications. We recommend the format proposed by [the FORCE11 Data Citation Principles](#).

Plagiarism

Plagiarism, where someone assumes another's ideas, words, or other creative expression as one's own, is a clear violation of scientific ethics. Plagiarism may also involve a violation of copyright law, punishable by legal action.

Plagiarism includes the following:

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- Copying equations, figures or tables from someone else's paper without properly citing the source and/or without permission from the original author or the copyright holder.

Please note that all submissions are thoroughly checked for plagiarism. **If a plagiarism detection software is used, state here the name of the software.**

Any manuscript that shows obvious signs of plagiarism will be automatically rejected **and define other sanctions (if any).**

In case plagiarism is discovered in a paper that has already been published by the journal, it will be retracted in accordance with the procedure described below under Retraction policy, **and authors will define other sanctions (if any).**

Conflict of interest

Authors should disclose in their manuscript any financial or other substantive conflict of interest that might have influenced the presented results or their interpretation. If there is no conflict of interest to declare, the following standard statement should be added: 'No conflict of interest was disclosed'.

Software (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). **Author 4:** Methodology (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). **Author 5:** Conceptualization (supporting); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review and editing (equal). More information: [How to Implement CRediT](#).

Conflict of interest may be of non-financial or financial nature. Examples of the conflict of interest include (but are not limited to):

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- individuals or their funding organization or employer holding (or applying for) related patents;
- official affiliations and memberships with interest groups relating to the content of the publication;
- familiar, political, religious, or ideological competing interests.

Authors from pharmaceutical companies, or other commercial organizations that sponsor clinical or field trials or other research studies, should declare these as competing interests on submission. The relationship of each author to such an organization should be explained in the 'Conflict of interest' section. Publications in the journal must not contain content advertising any commercial products.

Fundamental errors in published works

When an author discovers a significant error or inaccuracy in their own published work, it is the author's obligation to promptly notify the journal Editor or publisher and cooperate with the Editor to retract or correct the paper.

By submitting a manuscript the authors agree to abide by the *Journal's title's* Editorial Policies.

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ORCID registration provides a unique and persistent digital identifier for the account that enables accurate attribution and improves the discoverability of published papers, ensuring that the correct author receives the correct credit for their work.

Funding information

If a paper is a result of the funded project, authors are required to specify funding sources according to their contracts with the funder.

Reviewers' responsibilities

Reviewers are required to provide written, competent and unbiased feedback in a timely manner on the scholarly merits and the scientific value of the manuscript.

The reviewers assess manuscript for the compliance with the profile of the journal, the relevance of the investigated topic and applied methods, the originality and scientific relevance of information presented in the manuscript, the presentation style and scholarly apparatus.

Reviewers should alert the Editor to any well-founded suspicions or the knowledge of possible violations of ethical standards by the authors. Reviewers should recognize relevant published works that have not been cited by the authors and alert the Editor to substantial similarities between a reviewed manuscript and any manuscript published or under consideration for publication elsewhere, in the event they are aware of such. Reviewers should also alert the Editor to a parallel submission of the same manuscript to another journal, in the event they are aware of such.

Reviewers must not have conflict of interest with respect to the research, the authors and/or the funding sources for the research. If such conflicts exist, the reviewers must report them to the Editor without delay.

Any selected reviewer who feels unqualified to review the research reported in a manuscript or knows that its prompt review will be impossible should notify the Editor without delay.

Reviews must be conducted objectively. Personal criticism of the author is inappropriate. Reviewers should express their views clearly with supporting arguments.

Any manuscripts received for review must be treated as confidential documents. Reviewers must not use unpublished materials disclosed in submitted manuscripts without the express written consent of the authors. The information and ideas presented in submitted manuscripts shall be kept confidential and must not be used for personal gain.

Peer review

The submitted manuscripts are subject to a peer review process. The purpose of peer review is to assist the **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board** in making editorial decisions and through the editorial communication with the author it may also assist the author in improving the manuscript.

Define the type of peer review.¹⁶

The number of peer reviewers.¹⁷

It is recommended to define the time frame within which the peer review procedure is normally completed!

The choice of reviewers is at the discretion of the **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board**.¹⁸ The reviewers must be knowledgeable about the subject area of the

¹⁶Double blind / single blind / Open

¹⁷You can also publish a list of all regular peer reviewers by name on the journal website. This way, they receive recognition for their work, while the blind peer-review process is still preserved, since authors cannot tell who has reviewed their article.

¹⁸This is a typical situation. In journals with several section editors, reviewers are commonly assigned by section editors.

manuscript; they must not be from the authors' own institution and they should not have recent joint publications with any of the authors.

Describe the peer review process in greater detail.¹⁹

All of the reviewers of a manuscript act independently and they are not aware of each other's identities.²⁰ If the decisions of the two reviewers are not the same (accept/reject), the **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board** may assign additional reviewers.

During the review process, the **Editor / Editor-in-Chief / Section Editor / Editorial Board** may require authors to provide additional information (including raw data) if they are necessary for the evaluation of the scholarly merit of the manuscript. These materials shall be kept confidential and must not be used for personal gain.

The editorial team shall ensure reasonable quality control for the reviews. With respect to reviewers whose reviews are convincingly questioned by authors, special attention will be paid to ensure that the reviews are objective and high in academic standard. When there is any doubt with regard to the objectivity of the reviews or quality of the review, additional reviewers will be assigned.

Members of the editorial team/board/guest editors are permitted to submit their own papers to the journal. In cases where an author is associated with the journal, they will be removed from all editorial tasks for that paper and another member of the team will be assigned responsibility for overseeing peer review.

Post-publication discussions

Journal's title encourages post-publication debate either through letters to the editor, or on an external moderated site, such as [PubPeer](#).

Use of Large Language Models and generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools

Journal's title conforms to the [World Association of Medical Editors \(WAME\)](#)

¹⁹Some suggestions:

If a reviewer's evaluation form is used: In the main review phase, the Editor sends submitted manuscripts to **the number of reviewers** experts in the field. The reviewers' evaluation form contains a checklist in order to help reviewers cover all aspects that can decide the fate of a submission. In the final section of the evaluation form, the reviewers must include observations and suggestions aimed at improving the submitted manuscript; these are sent to authors, without the names of the reviewers.

Single-blind peer review: All of the reviewers of a manuscript remain anonymous to the authors before, during and after the evaluation process.

Double-blind peer review: All of the reviewers of a manuscript remain anonymous to the authors before, during and after the evaluation process and the authors remain anonymous to reviewers until the end of the review procedure.

²⁰Except in case of open review.

[recommendations on chat bots, ChatGPT and scholarly manuscripts](#) and the [Committee on Publication Ethics \(COPE\)'s position statement on Authorship and AI tools](#).

AI bots such as ChatGPT cannot be listed as authors on your submission.

Authors must clearly indicate the use of tools based on large language models and generative AI for data or code generation, data collection, cleaning, analysis, or interpretation, (which tool was used and for what purpose), preferably in the methods or acknowledgements sections. Photography, videos or illustrations created wholly or partly using generative AI are not considered acceptable. The use of non-generative machine learning tools to manipulate, combine or enhance existing images or figures should be disclosed in the relevant caption upon submission to allow a case-by-case review. Concealing the use of AI tools is unethical. The use of AI-based tools for copyediting and spell checking does not need to be declared.

AI outputs should not be cited as primary sources for backing up specific claims.

Editors and Reviewers must ensure the confidentiality of the editorial work and the peer review process. Editors must not share information about submitted manuscripts or peer review reports with any tools based on large language models and generative AI. Reviewers must not use any tools based on large language models and generative AI to generate review reports. Concealing the use of AI tools is unethical and undermines transparency in editorial work and peer review. The editorial and review processes are confidential, and using AI tools on the manuscript makes it public, violating the confidentiality principle, disclosing confidential information in public, and compromising transparency.

Procedures for dealing with complaints and appeals

Anyone may inform the editors and/or Editorial Staff at any time of suspected unethical behaviour or any type of misconduct by giving the necessary information/evidence to start an investigation.

Investigation

- **Editor / Editor-in-Chief** will consult with the **Section Editors / Editorial Board** on decisions regarding the initiation of an investigation.
- During an investigation, any evidence should be treated as strictly confidential and only made available to those strictly involved in investigating.
- The accused will always be given the chance to respond to any charges made against them.
- If it is judged at the end of the investigation that misconduct has occurred, then it will be classified as either minor or serious.

Minor misconduct

Minor misconduct will be dealt directly with those involved without involving any other parties, e.g.:

- Communicating to authors/reviewers whenever a minor issue involving misunderstanding or misapplication of academic standards has occurred.

- A warning letter to an author or reviewer regarding fairly minor misconduct.

Major misconduct

The **Editor / Editor-in-Chief**, in consultation with the **Section Editors / Editorial Board**, and, when appropriate, further consultation with a small group of experts should make any decision regarding the course of action to be taken using the evidence available. The possible outcomes are as follows (these can be used separately or jointly):

- Publication of a formal announcement or editorial describing the misconduct.
- Informing the author's (or reviewer's) head of department or employer of any misconduct by means of a formal letter.
- The formal, announced retraction of a contribution from the journal in accordance with the Retraction Policy (see below).
- A ban on submissions from an individual for a defined period.
- Referring a case to a professional organization or legal authority for further investigation and action.

When dealing with complaints and appeals, the editorial team will rely on the guidelines and recommendations provided by the Committee on Publication Ethics ([COPE](#)).

Retraction policy

The infringement of the legal limitations of the publisher, copyright holder or author(s), the violation of professional ethical codes and research misconduct, such as multiple submissions, duplicate or overlapping publication, bogus claims of authorship, plagiarism, fraudulent use of data and data fabrication, undisclosed use of tools based on large language models and generative AI, honest errors reported by the authors (for example, errors due to the mixing up of samples or use of a scientific tool or equipment that is found subsequently to be faulty), unethical research or any major misconduct require retraction of an article. Occasionally a retraction can be used to correct errors in submission or publication.

For any retracted article, the reason for retraction and who is instigating the retraction will be clearly stated in the Retraction notice. Standards for dealing with retractions have been developed by a number of library and scholarly bodies, and this practice has been adopted for article retraction by *Journal's title*:

- In the electronic version of the retraction note, a link is made to the original article.
- On the landing page of the original article, a link is made to the retraction note where it is clearly stated that the article has been retracted.
- The original article is retained unchanged, save for a watermark on the PDF indicating on each page that it is "retracted."

Research data, code, protocol sharing, and preregistration²¹

Research data sharing

Journal encourages/requests authors to share research data that are required for confirming the results published in the manuscript and/or enhance the published manuscript under the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. We encourage authors to share supporting software applications, high-resolution images, background datasets, sound or video clips, large appendices, data tables and other relevant items that cannot be included in the article.

The preferred mechanism for sharing research data is via data repositories. Authors may deposit relevant data in a [FAIR](#)-compliant repository – institutional, disciplinary, or general-purpose (e.g. [Zenodo](#)). If you need assistance in finding a FAIR compliant repository, check repository registries and search engines such as [DataCite Commons](#) and [Re3data.org](#). Authors should also provide via the repository any information needed to replicate, validate, and/or reuse the results / their study and analysis of the research data. This includes details of any software, instruments and other tools used to process the results. Where possible, the tools and instruments themselves should also be provided. In repositories, a DOI will be assigned to each research data file, enabling the research data to be cited the same way as publications. Authors affirm that data protection regulations, ethical standards, third party copyright and other rights have been respected in the process of collecting, processing and sharing data.

Exceptions: We recognize that open sharing of data may not always be feasible. Exceptions to open access to research data underlying publications include the following: obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, the obligation to protect personal data and other legitimate constraints. Where open access is not provided to the data needed to validate the conclusions of a publication that reports original results, authors should make metadata available explaining the research and access rules to the data.

Ethical and security considerations

If data access is restricted for ethical or security reasons, the manuscript must include:

- a description of the restrictions on the data;
- what, if anything, the relevant Institutional Review Board (IRB) or equivalent said about the data sharing; and
- all necessary information required for a reader or reviewer to apply for access to the data and the conditions under which access will be granted.

²¹Additional information about journal data policies: Hrynaszkiewicz, Iain, Natasha Simons, Azhar Hussain, Rebecca Grant, and Simon Goudie. 2020. ‘Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers’. *Data Science Journal* 19 (1): 5. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-005>.

Data protection issues

Where human data cannot be effectively de-identified, data must not be shared in order to protect participant privacy unless the individuals have given explicit written consent that their identifiable data can be made publicly available.

In instances where the data cannot be made available, the manuscript must include:

- an explanation of the data protection concern;
- any intermediary data that can be de-identified without compromising anonymity;
- what, if anything, the relevant Institutional Review Board (IRB) or equivalent said about data sharing; and
- where applicable, all necessary information required for a reader or peer reviewer to apply for access to the data and the conditions under which access will be granted.

Link to research data from a Data Availability Statement within the submitted paper, which will be made public upon publication. A 'Data Availability Statement'²² should be added to the submission, prior to the reference list, providing the details of the data availability, including the DOI linking to it. If the data is restricted in any way and/or is not being made available within the journal publication, a statement from the author should be provided to explain why.

Consider the following when depositing data related to a publication:

- Check whether a repository where the data is deposited has a sustainability model.
- The data must be deposited under an open license that permits unrestricted access (e.g., CC0, CC-BY). More restrictive licenses should only be used if there is a valid reason (e.g., legal).
- The deposited data must include a version that is in an open, non-proprietary format.
- The deposited data must have been labeled in such a way that a third party can make sense of it (e.g., sensible column headers, descriptions in a readme text file).
- Research involving human subjects, human material, or human data, must have been performed in accordance with the [Declaration of Helsinki](#). Where applicable, the

²²Don't forget to mention the Data Availability Statement in Author Guidelines and include it in the manuscript template, if you provide one. The Data Availability statements should take one of the following forms (or a combination of more than one if required for multiple types of research data):

- The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available in the [NAME] repository, [PERSISTENT WEB LINK TO DATASETS]
- The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are not publicly available due [REASON WHY DATA ARE NOT PUBLIC] but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.
- The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.
- Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.
- All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article [and its supplementary information files].
- The data that support the findings of this study are available from [third party name] but restrictions apply to the availability of these data, which were used under license for the current study, and so are not publicly available. Data are however available from the authors upon reasonable request and with permission of [third party name].

The phrasing has been taken from: Hrynaszkiewicz, Iain, Natasha Simons, Azhar Hussain, Rebecca Grant, and Simon Goudie. 2020. 'Developing a Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers'. *Data Science Journal* 19 (1): 5. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-005>.

studies must have been approved by an appropriate Ethics Committee. The identity of the research subject should be anonymized whenever possible. For research involving human subjects, informed consent to participate in the study must be obtained from participants (or their legal guardian).

Code sharing

Authors are encouraged to share any code used in their work, especially author-generated code. If commercial software was used, its name and version should be provided. This information can be included in the *Methods* section.

When feasible, code should be deposited in a public repository with a persistent identifier and version control. Open-source licensing is recommended. Deposited code should include:

- Installation and usage instructions
- Operating system details
- Programming language and data format information
- Software dependencies (version, toolboxes, modules)
- Documentation for reproducibility, including purpose explanations
- Actual or sample data with log files or equivalent documentation

For studies using custom code or mathematical algorithms essential to the conclusions, a Code Availability Statement must be included. This statement should specify code description, access details, repository identifier, and any access restrictions. It should be provided as a separate section following the Data Availability Statement.

Experimental protocols sharing

Authors are encouraged to share step-by-step research protocols to facilitate replication and further research. These can be uploaded to a protocol-sharing platform of choice or a repository, such as [Protocols.io](https://www.protocols.io/). If such protocols are available, please provide a DOI or other citation details with submission.

Preregistration

The journal **Journal title** supports study pre-registration (including clinical trials) and pre-registration of analysis plans in public repositories, for example [OSF Registries](https://osf.io/). Authors should indicate at submission whether any part of their study was preregistered. If so, they must include an active link to the preregistration in the Methods section and specify the preregistration date. Any deviations from the preregistered protocol should be disclosed, along with the reasons for those changes.

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- 'Guidance'. COPE: Committee on Publication Ethics. (accessed 2025-02-09). <https://publicationethics.org/guidance>. (accessed 2025-02-09).
- *Policies*. Open Research Europe. <https://open-research->

- europe.ec.europa.eu/about/policies (accessed 2025-01-08).
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 - 'Recommendations on the Use of AI in Scholarly Communication'. 2024. EASE. 25 September 2024. <https://ease.org.uk/2024/09/recommendations-on-the-use-of-ai-in-scholarly-communication/>. (accessed 2025-02-07)

Annex 2. Supporting documents

To avoid the risks of disputes over ethical issues, conflicts of interest, or copyright and licensing, it is important to obtain clear assurances from authors before publication. This annex provides templates for:

- Authorship statement – confirming originality, authorship, and compliance with ethical standards;
- Conflict of interest statement – disclosing any personal or financial interests that may have influenced the research;
- Licence agreement – granting the publisher permission to publish and distribute the article, and defining the terms under which it may be shared and reused.

Journals managing the submission process via email can offer a document based on these templates to authors to download, fill out and sign. Journals managing these processes via the journal management system (such as OJS, Janeway or Kotahi) can include these questions into submission checklists. This is a generic template that can be enriched with more specific questions.

Author statement template

By signing the Author statement authors formally confirm the originality, authorship, and compliance with ethical standards, as well as that all co-authors have approved the final version for publication.

Author statement

I confirm that the manuscript [Title] is aligned with the relevant Authors guidelines and the Authors' responsibilities defined in the Journal policies. I am also aware of the publisher's Retraction Policy.

For further information, see [\(relevant URLs from the journal's / publisher's website\)](#).

- The Manuscript I have submitted to the journal is original, has been written by the stated authors and has not been published elsewhere. (Posting of preprints on preprint servers or repositories is not considered prior publication.)
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- All authors have given the final approval of the submitted manuscript.
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Conflict of Interest statement template

By signing a conflict of interest authors let readers know if they have any personal or financial interests that could have influenced their research. This helps maintain the integrity and credibility of the published work.

Conflict of Interest statement

A conflict of interest may exist if you have financial, personal, or professional relationships that could influence your objectivity in the research, writing, or review process. Authors are required to disclose all and any potential conflicts of interest.

Financial Interests

Do you or any of the authors have any financial relationships with organizations that may have an interest in the submitted work (e.g., employment, grants, stocks, patents, or other financial interests)?

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Do you or any of the authors have any personal relationships that could bias the research or review process (e.g., family relationships, close personal friendships, etc.)?

Professional Relationships

Do you or any of the authors have any professional relationships that could affect the objectivity of the manuscript (e.g., membership in organizations, advisory roles, etc.)?

Other Potential Conflicts

Are there any other relationships, interests, or activities that could be perceived as a conflict of interest?

If the answer to any of these questions is “Yes”, please provide additional details:

Declaration of No Conflict of Interest:

(If there are no conflicts of interest to declare)

- I confirm that I have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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